

Synthesis of Cylindrical Metasurfaces through Tailoring the Propagation Characteristics of Electromagnetic Waves

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Abstract – This paper presents a fast and efficient approach for designing metasurfaces that conform to curved geometries. We introduce analytical tools that allow for the efficient extraction of parameters related to electromagnetic wave propagation along cylindrical metasurfaces, enabling the design of diverse components with minimal curvature-induced effects. The synthesis method is demonstrated through the design of a cylindrical leaky-wave antenna.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the recent years, planar leaky-wave metasurface antennas have been extensively researched, and well-established methods exist for their analysis and synthesis within the electromagnetic community. These metasurfaces are not only useful for designing leaky-wave antennas but also play a key role in developing various electromagnetic components such as microwave lenses, polarization converters, beam splitters, and highly directive reflective arrays. The increasing demand for machine-to-machine and human-to-machine communication, particularly with the expansion of 5G and the anticipated emergence of 6G networks, has highlighted the need for antennas that can conform to curved surfaces. However, research on curved metasurfaces remains in its early stages, and only a few studies have addressed the design of curved leaky-wave metasurface antennas (one such effort is discussed in [1]). The curvature of these structures presents new challenges, as it directly influences the antenna's radiation pattern — an issue not encountered in planar designs [1]–[3].

In this paper, we explore the behavior of electromagnetic waves as they propagate along cylindrical metasurface structures and investigate the possibilities of tailoring the wave propagation characteristics. By modifying the propagation properties, we demonstrate how it is possible to design curved leaky-wave metasurface antennas with an approach similar to that used for planar configurations.

II. PROPAGATION OF ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVES ALONG CYLINDRICAL METASURFACE STRUCTURE

In planar configurations, normally polarized surface waves excited by a line current source propagate without attenuation: losses can only emerge due to losses of the dielectric layer. Planar metasurface leaky-wave antennas exploit the interaction between lossless surface waves and a quasi-periodic surface impedance perturbation to generate radiation by converting the $n = -1$ Floquet Harmonic to a fast wave and allowing it to radiate. When the planar grounded dielectric slab with a metasurface coating is bent into a cylindrical shape, along with the more complex geometry the analysis procedure becomes significantly more demanding. This introduces additional losses as a result of curvature and dielectric thickness, i.e. the curved structure transforms non radiating surface waves into radiating creeping waves, which lack precise directional control. To mitigate these effects, the metasurface impedance must be carefully designed to minimize creeping wave losses and impose the correct phase profile for the desired radiation pattern.

To analyze creeping wave propagation on the infinite (in \hat{z} -direction) dielectric coated cylinder covered with a thin layer of sheet reactance (essentially a metasurface) and excited by a radially oriented electric current in the dielectric layer, we derive a dispersion relation using the transverse resonance method:

$$H_{\nu}^{\prime(2)}(k_0 b) - j (C^H \parallel C^{MTS}) H_{\nu}^{(2)}(k_0 b) = 0. \quad (1)$$

Here k_0 is the free space wave number, b is the outer radius of the PEC cylinder dielectric coating, $H_{\nu}^{(2)}$ and $H_{\nu}^{\prime(2)}$ are the Hankel function of the second kind of complex order ν and its derivative [4], C^H is the surface impedance

for TE_z polarization (excited by the radially oriented electric current) of the dielectric coating [5][6], and C^{MTS} normalized surface impedance of the thin metasurface layer. Solutions to the equation 1 are complex numbers ν_m which define the propagation constant of the dominant creeping wave mode m with imaginary part of the ν_m defining creeping wave losses due to radiation, and real part defining phase dependency of the creeping wave. Electrical field excited by a radially oriented current source E_ϕ then consists of two waves traveling in $+\hat{\phi}$ and $-\hat{\phi}$ directions, and is proportional to:

$$E_\phi(\rho, \phi) \sim \left(e^{-j\nu_1\phi} + e^{-j\nu_1(2\pi-\phi)} \right). \quad (2)$$

The validity of the presented theory is verified against the case with parameters $k_0b = 20$, relative permittivity of the dielectric $\epsilon_r = 4$, $C^{MTS}\eta_0 = -j200 \Omega$ and thickness of the dielectric layer $h = \lambda_0/20$, where λ_0 is the free space wavelength. Figure 1 shows the relative E_ϕ -field distribution in the vicinity of the grounded dielectric coated PEC cylinder with and without the metasurface cover calculated using the creeping wave representation and in-house MoM software for analyzing cylindrical metasurface structures. Figure 1 also reveals that it is possible to drastically reduce creeping wave radiation by covering the dielectric with the metasurface of sufficient reactance by effectively slowing down the propagating creeping wave.

Fig. 1: Relative E_ϕ -field distribution in the vicinity of the grounded dielectric coated PEC cylinder: (a) without the metasurface; (b) with the metasurface of $C^{MTS}\eta_0 = -j200 \Omega$.

III. EXAMPLE: CYLINDRICAL METASURFACE ANTENNA WITH PENCIL BEAM RADIATION PATTERN DESIGN

Based on the theory presented in the previous section, it is possible to design a cylindrical metasurface antenna with the layout shown in Figure 2a. The example antenna is split into three equal sections with different propagation properties: an unmodulated guide, a modulated radiator, and an absorber for attenuating creeping waves in the $-\hat{\phi}$ -direction. The design steps include first determining the mean surface reactance profile for which the creeping wave losses are negligible for a given operating frequency and dimensions of the cylinder and thickness of the substrate. Second step is retrieving the surface reactance profile for the desired near field distribution using the holographic inspired approach, and in the final step dividing the surface reactance profile to sub-wavelength cells. Antenna with a pencil beam radiation pattern in $\phi = 30^\circ$ direction is designed, and its required opaque surface reactance is shown in Fig. 2b. Radiation patterns of the example antenna are calculated using in-house MoM software and verified against the commercial CST Suite simulations and shown in Figure 3a. It can be seen that the results match extraordinary. Near field distribution of the antenna is shown in Figure 3b. These results demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed design approach and the potential of radiation control that can be achieved even on conformal (i.e. curved) shapes.

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Fig. 2: Cylindrical metasurface antenna with pencil beam radiation pattern: (a) layout; (b) required opaque surface reactance distribution for modulated part of the antenna. The parameters of the antenna are: $f = 24$ GHz, $b = 101.5$ mm, dielectric thickness $b - a = 1.5$ mm, permittivity $\epsilon_r = 2.25$, and modulation factor $M = 0.2$.

Fig. 3: Radiation patterns of the example antenna: (a) far field; (b) near field in-time snapshot.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Foroozesh, R. Paknys, D. R. Jackson, and J.-J. Laurin, "Beam focusing using backward-radiating waves on conformal leaky-wave antennas based on a metal strip grating," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 63, no. 11, pp. 4667–4677, 2015.
- [2] Z. Sipus, M. Bosiljevac, and A. Grbic, "Modelling cascaded cylindrical metasurfaces using sheet impedances and a transmission matrix formulation," *IET Microw. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 12, pp. 1041–1047, June 2018.
- [3] D. Mikulić, M. Bosiljevac, C. Craeye, Z. Šipuš, "Propagation of Electromagnetic Waves along Cylindrical Metasurface Structure," in *2025 19th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, pp. 1–5, 2025.
- [4] R. Paknys, "Evaluation of hankel functions with complex argument and complex order," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 40, no. 5, pp. 569–578, 1992.
- [5] R. Paknys and D. Jackson, "The relation between creeping waves, leaky waves, and surface waves," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 898–907, 2005.
- [6] R. Paknys and N. Wang, "Creeping wave propagation constants and modal impedance for a dielectric coated cylinder," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 674–680, 1986.